

Computed tomography grey-white matter ratio in an elderly population: Rationale and design of a retrospective cross-sectional study

Authors

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Abstract

Introduction

A grey-white matter ratio (GWR) below 1.10 on head computed tomography (CT) predict poor functional outcome in an unconscious cardiac arrest population with high specificity, moderate sensitivity and good interrater agreement. However, little is known about GWR values on CT in patients without cardiac arrest.

We here present the protocol of an analysis of GWR at the basal ganglia level on CTs from patients age- and gender matched to a cardiac arrest-population. We hypothesise that zero percent will have a GWR below 1.10.

Methods

In a retrospective cross-sectional study, routine CTs from awake patients, age- and gender matched to a cardiac arrest population, were collected. CTs without present intracranial pathology will be individually assessed by three raters. GWR will be quantified manually by 0.1 and 0.2 cm² circular regions of interest (ROIs) placed at the basal ganglia level in the putamen, the caudate nucleus (caput), the posterior limb of the internal capsule, and the genu corpus callosum bilaterally.

Bland-Altman plots will be presented with mean, upper and lower limits of agreement and bias with 95 % confidence intervals for the absolute GWR of each patient between the raters.

Results

Between January- and August of 2021 228 CTs were collected. Forty-three patients (61 CTs) were excluded due to intracranial haemorrhage (n=19), acute infarction (n=15), tumour/metastases (n=5), other (n=2), and artefacts (n=2). Twelve of the remaining 167 CTs were two CTs from the identical patient. In total 155 CTs were analysed.

Conclusion

The result from this retrospective trial will give an insight in how GWR values at the basal ganglia level are distributed in an elderly population without cardiac arrest.

Introduction

Hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy (HIE) is the main cause of death after cardiac arrest and among cardiac arrest-survivors permanent neurological impairments are often seen (1). To predict functional outcome in unconscious cardiac arrest patients, head computed tomography (CT) is a frequently used guideline recommended tool (2, 3).

On CT the HIE can be detected as brain oedema. In addition to the sulcal effacement from the vasogenic oedema, the cytotoxic oedema in neurons results in a reduced difference between the grey- and white matter, since the white matter remains unaffected longer (4). The difference between the grey- and white matter can be quantified by measuring the density in Hounsfield units (HU) in specific grey and white matter areas and calculating the grey- white matter ratio (GWR) (5). This is the only guideline-recommended method to quantify the extent of HIE on CT (1).

We previously showed that standardised and automated assessment of CT reliably could predict poor functional outcome in patients unconscious >48 hours after CA. The pre-specified GWR cut-off <1.10 resulted in 100% specificity (min-max 100-100) and 39% median sensitivity (min-max 31-47) for seven blinded raters outplacing eight circular 0.1 cm² regions of interest at the basal ganglia level. The automated quantitative CT assessment was non inferior to the manual quantitative assessment, offering an appealing alternative (6).

Several studies have suggested GWR cut-offs between 1.07 – 1.23 as specific for prediction of poor functional outcome in unconscious CA patients (7). However, there is a knowledge gap concerning the average GWR at the basal ganglia level in the aging normal population (8-11).

The aim of the planned study is to describe the GWR at the basal ganglia level in a reference group to our unconscious CA population. We hypothesise that no patient in the reference group will have a GWR <1.10.

Methods

Study design

This is a retrospective cross-sectional observational single centre study from Helsingborg Hospital, Sweden of patients examined with CT between 1st of January – 17th of August 2021.

Ethics and Patient selection

Ethical approval was obtained from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority in June 2022. From the 1st of January 2021 CTs performed at Helsingborg Hospital on one of the Radiology department's computed tomographies were selected. Inclusion criteria were awake adults (>18 years) referred to CT due to stroke- or transient ischaemic attack symptoms. The population was filtered to match a CA-population regarding age and gender (mean age 70 years, 65% men). One of the raters read the rereferrals and the original radiology reports and excluded patients with recent cardiac arrest and/or reports describing signs of present intracranial pathology. All CTs were reviewed visually and CTs with artefacts interfering with reliable measurements were excluded. CTs were anonymized apart from the date and time for the CT, and the age and gender of the patient.

Technical requirements and manual CT assessment

All CTs were performed at the identical Siemens Somatom Definition Flash at a tube voltage of 120 kV. All CTs will be interpreted with axial slices with a slice thickness of 5 mm using a virtual private network (VPN) secured platform (Human Observer Net) (12). Three raters (one consultant in neuroradiology, one neurologist, and one specialist in general radiology) from two countries will individually place circular 0.1 cm² regions of interest at the basal ganglia level; in the putamen, the caudate nucleus (caput), the posterior limb of the internal capsule, and in the genu corpus callosum bilaterally as described previously (6, 13). When all 155 CTs are rated, the raters will do outplacement of ROIs in the same locations but with circular ROIs measuring 0.2 cm².

GWR calculations

GWR will be calculated as the sum of the radiodensity (HU) of the grey matter ROIs divided by the sum of the radiodensity of the white matter ROIs as described previously (6, 13).

Statistical analysis

The results will be reported according to STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) (14).

We will present the proportion with $GWR < 1.1$ with a 95% confidence interval. We assume that the proportion with $GWR < 1.1$ will be 0 and we will calculate the confidence intervals using Wilson's score method. A confidence interval with an upper limit of 0.024 is deemed acceptable and then need to include 155 individuals.

The interrater agreement using the 0.1 cm² respectively the 0.2 cm² ROIs will be presented with Bland-Altman plots with mean, upper and lower limits of agreement and bias with 95 % confidence intervals for the absolute GWR of each patient between the raters, three couples.

Preliminary data

In total 228 CTs performed between January- and August of 2021 were collected. Forty-three patients (61 CTs) were excluded due to intracranial haemorrhage (n=19), acute infarction (n=15), tumour/metastases (n=5), other (n=2), and artefacts interfering with reliable measurements (n=2). Twelve of the remaining 167 CTs were two CTs from the identical patient. In total 155 CTs will be analysed (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Flowchart of patient inclusion and exclusion

Discussion

Despite the fact that GWR on CTs has been studied for long in the cardiac arrest population, there is a knowledge gap concerning the distribution of GWR in the normal population (8-11, 15-17). We want to examine whether age matched patients routinely examined with CT in the emergency department present with GWR below 1.1, a cut-off considered indicative of poor functional outcome after CA.

Conclusion

The result from this retrospective trial will give an insight in how the GWR are distributed in an elderly population without cardiac arrest.

References

1. Nolan JP, Sandroni C, Böttiger BW, Cariou A, Cronberg T, Friberg H, et al. European Resuscitation Council and European Society of Intensive Care Medicine guidelines 2021: post-resuscitation care. *Intensive Care Med.* 2021;47(4):369-421.
2. Elmer J, Steinberg A, Callaway CW. Paucity of neuroprognostic testing after cardiac arrest in the United States. *Resuscitation.* 2023;188:109762.
3. Rajajee V, Muehlschlegel S, Wartenberg KE, Alexander SA, Busl KM, Chou SHY, et al. Guidelines for Neuroprognostication in Comatose Adult Survivors of Cardiac Arrest. *Neurocrit Care.* 2023;38(3):533-63.
4. Beekman R, Hirsch KG. Brain imaging after cardiac arrest. *Curr Opin Crit Care.* 2023;29(3):192-8.
5. Metter RB, Rittenberger JC, Guyette FX, Callaway CW. Association between a quantitative CT scan measure of brain edema and outcome after cardiac arrest. *Resuscitation.* 2011;82(9):1180-5.
6. Lang M, Kenda M, Scheel M, Martola J, Wheeler M, Owen S, et al. Standardised and automated assessment of head computed tomography reliably predicts poor functional outcome after cardiac arrest: a prospective multicentre study. *Intensive Care Med.* 2024;50(7):1096-107.
7. Sandroni C, Cronberg T, Sekhon M. Brain injury after cardiac arrest: pathophysiology, treatment, and prognosis. *Intensive Care Med.* 2021;47(12):1393-414.
8. Oh JH, Choi SP, Wee JH, Park JH. Inter-scanner variability in Hounsfield unit measured by CT of the brain and effect on gray-to-white matter ratio. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2019;37(4):680-4.
9. Weinstein A, Meredith ea. White and Gray Matter of the Brain Differentiated by Computed Tomography. *Radiology.* 1977;122:699-702.
10. Gado Mokhtar ea. Brain Parenchymal Density Measurements by CT in Demented Subjects and Normal Controls. *NEURORADIOLOGY.* 1983;147:703-10.
11. Torbey MT, Selim M, Knorr J, Bigelow C, Recht L. Quantitative analysis of the loss of distinction between gray and white matter in comatose patients after cardiac arrest. *Stroke.* 2000;31(9):2163-7.
12. Genske U, Jahnke P. Human Observer Net: A Platform Tool for Human Observer Studies of Image Data. *Radiology.* 2022;303(3):524-30.
13. Lang M, Leithner C, Scheel M, Kenda M, Cronberg T, Doring J, et al. Prognostic accuracy of head computed tomography for prediction of functional outcome after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest: Rationale and design of the prospective TTM2-CT-substudy. *Resusc Plus.* 2022;12:100316.
14. Cuschieri S. The STROBE guidelines. *Saudi J Anaesth.* 2019;13(Suppl 1):S31-s4.
15. Oh JH, Choi SP, Zhu JH, Kim SH, Park KN, Youn CS, et al. Differences in the gray-to-white matter ratio according to different computed tomography scanners for outcome prediction in post-cardiac arrest patients receiving target temperature management. *PLoS One.* 2021;16(10):e0258480.
16. Zhou F, Wang H, Jian M, Wang Z, He Y, Duan H, et al. Gray-White Matter Ratio at the Level of the Basal Ganglia as a Predictor of Neurologic Outcomes in Cardiac Arrest Survivors: A Literature Review. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2022;9:847089.

17. Cronberg T, Brizzi M, Liedholm LJ, Rosén I, Rubertsson S, Rylander C, et al. Neurological prognostication after cardiac arrest--recommendations from the Swedish Resuscitation Council. *Resuscitation*. 2013;84(7):867-72.